

A New Expression For The Areas of Rectangle and Square via Inscribed Ellipses and Integrals

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Prateek P Kulkarni

prateekkulkarni24@gmail.com

ABSTRACT:

The author proposes new integral-type representation of areas of squares and rectangles using inscribed ellipses.

I. The Idea

Inscribe an ellipse inside a rectangle. Then translate the bottom half of it to be a tangent to the horizontal (x axis). Then, area under this bottom half, plus the area of ellipse divided by 2 and finally the whole sum divided by 2 is precisely what the equation means for any regular rectangle.

By similar means, the equation for square can also be obtained.

II. The Theorem and Proof

Theorem: For a rectangle enclosed by $(a,b) \forall a,b > 0$, the area of rectangle is given by:

$$ab = \frac{1}{2} \left(\int_{-a}^a \left(-\frac{b}{a} \sqrt{a^2 - x^2} + b \right) dx + \frac{ab}{2} \pi \right)$$

And that of a square whose side is a is given by:

$$a^2 = \int_{-a}^a \left(-\sqrt{a^2 - x^2} + \frac{a}{2} \right) dx + \frac{a^2}{2} \pi$$

Proof:

Rearranging the equation as follows:

$$\int_{-a}^a \left(-\frac{b}{a} \sqrt{a^2 - x^2} + b \right) dx = -\frac{b}{a} \int_{-a}^a \sqrt{a^2 - x^2} dx + [bx]_{-a}^a$$

Now, the left-hand side of the equation is:

$$= \left[-\frac{b}{a} \int_{-a}^a \frac{x\sqrt{a^2-x^2}}{2} + \frac{a^2}{2} \sin^{-1} \frac{x}{a} dx \right]_{-a}^a + 2ab$$

Integrating by parts,

$$-\frac{b}{a} \left[\frac{a^2 \pi}{2 \cdot 2} - \frac{a^2 (-\pi)}{2 \cdot 2} \right] + 2ab = 2ab - \frac{b}{a} \left(\frac{\pi a^2}{2} \right)$$

Simplifying which yields $\left(2 - \frac{\pi}{2} \right) ab$.

If we multiply both sides of the obtained equation by 2, we notice that right side of the equation is the area of square with sides $a, 2b$ and it is clearly obvious that $a = 2b$, thus using this fact, we have the following expression for the area of a square:

$$\int_{-a}^a \left(-\sqrt{a^2 - x^2} + \frac{a}{2} \right) dx + \frac{a^2}{2} \pi = 2ba = a^2$$

This completes the proof. ■
